

The Role of Organizational Culture in Facilitating Employee Job Satisfaction in Emerald Group

Mohamed Haffar, Muhammad Abdul Aziz, Ahmad Ghoneim

Abstract—The importance of having a good organizational culture that supports employee job satisfaction has fascinated both the business and academic world because of a tantalizing promise: culture can be fundamental to the enhancement of financial performance. This promise has led to growing interest for both researchers and practitioners in attempting to understand the influence of organizational culture on employees' satisfaction and organizational performance. Even though the relationship between organizational culture and employee job satisfaction have gained attention in the literature, the majority of studies have been conducted within manufacturing organizations and tend to oversee the impact of culture on employee job satisfaction in a service-based environment. Thus, the main driving force of this study was to explore the role of organizational culture types in facilitating employee job satisfaction at Emerald Publishing Group. Interviews qualitative data analysis indicated that Emerald's culture dominated by adhocracy and clan culture values. In addition, the findings provided evidence, which demonstrated that group and adhocracy organizational culture types play key roles in facilitating employee job satisfaction in a service-based environment.

Keywords—Employee satisfaction, organizational culture, performance, service based environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

CONTEMPORARY organizations regard human resources as the most significant characteristic of a successful business, and for this purpose, plenty of studies have been conducted on this subject in the last three decades, with a wide range of themes [1]. Two of the widely studied topics in the field of Organizational Behavior and Human Resource Management have been 'organizational culture' and 'employee job satisfaction' in the last two centuries. Reference [2] asserted that due to the direct relation of these topics to human's nature and psych, various models and theories are developed to model and measure both of these topics. This claim is supported by the existing literature, which demonstrated that organizational culture plays a key role in improving the performance of the business through influencing employee job satisfaction [3]. According to [4], for a business to be successful, one of the objectives of the human resources manager must be to understand and measure the impact of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction.

Significant attention has recently been paid to the influence of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction.

Mohamed Haffar, Muhammad Abdul Aziz and Ahmad Ghoneim are with the Human Resources Management, Faculty of Management, Law and Social Sciences, University of Bradford, Bradford, BD7 1DP, UK (phone: 00441247238919, e-mail: m.haffar@bradford.ac.uk).

However, most studies tend to ignore the influence of culture on job satisfaction. For this reason, this exploratory study focused on the role of organizational culture in facilitating employee job satisfaction in an office-based environment, particularly at Emerald Publishing Group.

Emerald was selected because they are a well-recognized business with worldwide recognition. Emerald is a publication organization that aims to champion new ideas that advance the practice and research of business and management [5]. Emerald provides scholarly publisher of academic journals and books in the fields of management, business, education, library studies, health care, and engineering. The workplace environment of Emerald is office-based, which is suited to this specific study and thus chosen for this research. In retrospect, Emerald's outcomes and success is the result of the efforts of employees at all levels (functional, operational and senior). If all employees perform in accordance to the agreed standards, then Emerald's performance will be improved. For this reason, employee job satisfaction and performance is regarded as an important benchmark that translates into Emerald's outcomes and success, which makes it the backbone of the business.

II. THE CONCEPT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

In the study of organizations and their management, the concept of organizational culture (also known as corporate culture) has become progressively more important, and the volume of research in the field has improved dramatically since the early 1980s [4]. The term organizational climate was common in the literature of organization and management in the 1960s and 1970s, and both climate and culture were used interchangeably until the concept of organizational culture acknowledged itself as a distinctive research field [6]. Academic interest in organizational culture was mainly inspired by three management consultants' writers; namely, [7] – In Search of Excellence, [8] – Theory Z and [9] – Corporate Cultures. They argued that organizational culture is crucial for long-term success, because it influences the way employees value, feel, act, think and perceive workplace environment. Conversely, some research (for example, [10], [11]) propounded that the relationship between culture and organizational effectiveness is not easy to identify. Reference [12] asserted that although culture is characterized as difficult to change, it is portrayed as a glue that holds the entire organization together. Organizational culture has been studied for decades, as the fact that distinguishes between employees' expectations and values [13].

Although there are numerous definitions of organizational culture, researchers such as [14] and [16] have reached

agreement that it refers to a system of behavior, beliefs and values shared between workers. These researchers mainly supported the definition of by [17] who proposed that “organizational culture is the pattern of basic assumptions that a group has invented, or discovered in learning to cope with its problems of external adaptation and internal integration, and that have worked well enough to be considered valid and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems”. According to [4], organizational culture shows the fundamental characteristics of an organization, which can be a source of sustainable competitive advantage if that culture is imperfectly inimitable, rare and valuable. Managerial practitioners and academics have come to the consensus that the culture of an organization is the “core competency”, which affects employees’ satisfaction and productivity and the organization as a whole [18].

Just like there are many perspectives and definitions into the notion of organizational culture, there are also great-deal of studies conducted attempting to know how to measure “culture” [19]. To understand the concept of organizational culture, it is important to critically analyze the studies that have contributed to the development of this notion by presenting measures of organizational culture. The literature is prolific in studies, for example, [20], [21] evaluated the different perspectives on organizational culture and came up with various instruments and dimensions to measure the culture of an organization.

Even though, there are various approaches to studying culture such Hofstede’s and Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner’s, they mainly tackled the issue from societal perspectives. The aim of the current study was to examine the role of organizational culture in facilitating employee job satisfaction. Therefore, the measurements of societal approaches towards organizational culture were not suitable and thus could not be considered

The “Competing Values Framework” (CVF) was developed by [22] and primarily focuses on the measurement of organizational culture, including a wide-range of organizational phenomena ranging from organizational quality, organizational design, organizational culture, and phases of life-cycle development, theories of effectiveness, management skills, and roles of human resource managers and leadership roles.

One of the most recognized models of organizational culture, the CVF is built on two main dimensions. The first dimensions looks at the focus of the organization and assesses whether it has an internal or external approach. The second dimension draws on the degree to which an organization focuses on stability and control in contrast to flexibility and individuality. Reference [23] noted that [22]’s model of two dimensions formed four dominant types of organizational culture; namely, hierarchy culture, market culture, adhocracy culture and clan culture (shown in Fig. 1). To determine the dominant culture of an organization, [21] developed another model called “Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument” (OCAI). The OCAI is an empirically reliable and validated instrument, as [1] argued modern-day researchers uses the

OCAI tool to analyze the effects of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction.

Fig. 1 Completing Values Framework [21]

III. EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION

A study conducted by [24] propounded that organizational culture influences various organizational variables such as organizational quality, organizational design, organizational culture, and phases of life-cycle development, theories of effectiveness, management skills, and roles of human resource managers and leadership roles. This is also supported by the literature where researchers [12], [10] suggested that organizational culture affects employee’s behaviors and attitudes. In a demonstration of this claim, [25] and [26] asserted that one of these behaviors and attitudes is employee job satisfaction, which is directly influenced by the culture of an organization.

Employee job satisfaction is one of the most widely studied phenomena in the field of organizational behavior and management, as it has been identified as an attitude that is key to quality working in the context of any organization [27]. Reference [28] has linked employee job satisfaction to significant organizational variables, such as commitment, turnover, productivity and absenteeism. The literature has pointed out to the scientific study of Taylor, where the correlation between employee job satisfaction and motivations was studied for the first time [29]. However, Taylor’s main piece of the jig-saw was the “Scientific Management” finding which noted that economic needs motivates employees to improve performance [19]. The classical era of scientific management was soon followed by the era of human relations that was mainly developed by Hawthorne’s studies in 1924. These studies claimed that the ‘human’ is the most important asset of the organization, and thus the focus should be on motivating the workforce and not economic needs as suggested by Taylorism. Hawthorne’s studies examined the effects of operational and physical workplace environment on employees’ job satisfaction and productivity [30].

Reference [31] defined employee job satisfaction as an “emotional reaction to work experience”. Reference [32] have also followed the same line of thinking by asserting it as “a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experience”. Another definition of this theme is by [33] who defined it as “the feelings a worker has about his job which are associated with perceived difference between what is expected as a fair and reasonable return and what is experienced, in relation to the alternatives available in a given situation”. Another key definition was presented by [53], who outlined employee job satisfaction as “an attitudinal variable that reflects how people feel about their jobs overall as well as about various aspects of them.

IV. EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION, ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP

Scholars in the field of organizational behavior have always been interested in identifying the factors that influence the attitudes and behaviors of the workers. Working condition was discovered as one of the factors that influences employee’s attitude [34]. Correspondingly, [35] argued that employee’s values are crucial aspects, because they shape the perception towards the organization. In their study of organizational culture, employee job satisfaction and commitment of the organization, [36] suggested that employee’s job satisfaction and the commitment of organization is negatively influenced by the bureaucratic culture. It has been argued by [37] propounded that employee job satisfaction is positively influenced by innovative organizational culture, bureaucratic organizational culture and supportive organizational culture, in a descending order.

The influence of organizational culture dimensions on employee job satisfaction is contested amongst researchers. For example, a study conducted by [38] revealed employee job satisfaction to be influenced by management and control, results-orientation and professionalism. Another study was carried out by [39] who found that organizations that recognize the performance of its employees leads to high job satisfaction. Conversely, [40] argued that immovability, respect for employee and assertiveness have a positive influence on employee job satisfaction. Therefore, the need for further investigation in this field is required to recognize the relationship between organizational culture and employee job satisfaction. This agreement is backed by [41] who inferred that only a few studies have examined the impact of distinct cultural values on employee job satisfaction.

The relationship between organizational culture and employee job satisfaction is widely discussed in the literature [42]. However, the need for advanced research was suggested by [43]’s findings, which proved that organizational culture is an important element that influences employee job satisfaction and improves productivity. The relationship between satisfied workforce and higher productivity was analyzed by [44] who propounded that when employees are happy, the entire organization is happy and that leads to improved performance, commitment and enhanced productivity. The problem is that most organizations do not understand this relationship and

only few have succeeded to maintain a happy workforce [45]. Reference [2] added that the correlation seems obvious, yet only a few organizations have invested time and energy into ensuring employees satisfaction.

Although there are four types of culture that were identified and examined by [21], only clan and adhocracy culture is the most influential in the literature, as [46] asserted the connection between clan and adhocracy culture are positively associated with employee job satisfaction. Researchers have characterized clan and adhocracy culture to be the most dominant in organizations that seek employee job satisfaction [47]. In support of these claims, [21] demonstrated that the reason why clan culture and adhocracy cultures are positively linked with employee job satisfaction is down to the fact that these types of organizational culture focus on their employees and not the hierarchy or market and provide them empowerment, autonomy and encourage team working and innovation. Conversely, in the market and hierarchy culture, employees are micro-managed, controlled and the leadership seeks efficiency-based coordination and organization [47], [48].

A study conducted by [10] explored the impact of corporation culture on employee satisfaction in the workplace, using a sample of 360 marketing professionals in American firms. Lund discovered that organizations with clan and adhocracy culture had higher level of employee job satisfaction as opposed to organizations that had hierarchy and market cultures. Other studies have confirmed the findings of Lund, for example, [47]’s study of employees in entrepreneurial organizations in Rawapindi and Islamabad, and [48]’s study of employees from different organizations in Pakistan discovered similar findings as [10]. These studies have identified the important relationship between organization culture types and employee job satisfaction and concluded two primary findings; firstly, organizations with clan and adhocracy culture satisfied their workforce and secondly employees working in a market and hierarchy culture were dissatisfied. Even though the majority of the studies backed these findings, [10]’s findings differed as he did not indicate any dissatisfaction, instead the study only concluded that there was lower level of employee job satisfaction, which is quite different.

A scarcity of studies within the literature has studied the relationship between organizational culture types and employee performance as result of job satisfaction [49]. These studies attempted to see the link between a market culture and employee performance, as the core value of this culture is to hit the targets and managers are seen as drivers to help the workforce achieve the results [21]. A study conducted by [15] on the role of organizational culture in contemporary organizations, found that for an organization to seek higher levels of employee job satisfaction and productivity, then a combination of clan, market and adhocracy cultures are required.

V. METHODOLOGY

The type of research chosen by the researcher was

exploratory because few previous studies exist. The methodology undertaken by this study was qualitative where semi-structured interviews were used to collect the data using mono method and cross-sectional time horizon. The research strategy chosen was the case study, which is an empirical in-depth inquiry about an organization (in this case, the Emerald Publishing Group). The researcher used this strategy to understand the role of organizational culture in facilitating employee job satisfaction in an office-based environment. The reason for choosing this strategy over the rest was down to the fact that this research aims to see the role of organizational culture in Emerald within a natural setting. Although, there were three different ways in case study strategy to conduct the research; namely, observations, interviews and questionnaires; the researcher only used interviews due to time and resources constraint.

The type of approach preferred by the researcher to carry out the research was to use semi-structured interviews conducted with different employees from the bottom line and middle management. The nature of the semi-structured interviews included questions that were slightly more open ended. To best fit the aim of the project, the researcher chose case study research strategy over survey research strategy because it offered more room for the data to be interpreted. The answers received from open ended questions can be a bit complicated and complex, and thus, the case study research strategy is the most suitable because there is room for data to be interpreted [50]. Furthermore, limited research has been carried out previously in this field, and therefore the consideration of existing theories will be constrained, as only few theories and research are available. In retrospect, the researcher has opted for case study research strategy as an empirical in-depth inquiry about an organization that allows the researcher to retain meaningful and holistic characteristics of events in real life. The above reasons highlight why a case study seemed the most effective research strategy in comparison to any other research strategy.

The population consisted of five different departments of around 15 employees selected randomly to share their experience of how organizational culture has influenced their satisfaction and productivity. The individuals that were selected for interview were from five different departments; namely, finance, operations, publications, human resources and marketing. The study was also making sure that the individuals interviewed had different level of experience to ensure an accurate and fair sample. Having respondents from various departments and hierarchical levels offers the researcher insight into the complete picture of employee's perspectives at Emerald [51].

To analyze the qualitative data, we followed the procedure by [51] and identified "patterns and themes". Also coding tools was used in the transcriptions if data were broken into smaller parts. Finally, the researcher made sure the research conducted complied with the Data Protection Act 1998 and did not disclose any personal data gathered from the participants without their consent, and submitted an Ethic Checklist Form for approval before undertaking any field

work.

VI. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Impact of Adhocracy Culture on Employee Job Satisfaction

The sample of interviewees depicted a weak, however encouraging influence of adhocracy culture on employee job satisfaction in Emerald, as the participants gained job satisfaction and components of dissatisfaction from adhocracy culture. The job satisfaction was emphasized by Respondent (1) who affirmed "I love my job because every day is different with new tasks and challenges, which is something that I like". This claim shows the employee job satisfaction is a result of the challenges provided by the adhocracy culture. Conversely, Respondent (10) highlighted the components of dissatisfaction offered by the job, "There are a lot of changes that takes place, over the last 10 years we have so many changes that made us employees think oh God what is going to happen next". The respondents identified coping with constant change as an element of dissatisfaction and suggested a need for the stability of hierarchy culture. These arguments are backed by the studies of [47] and [48] who found a weak but a positive correlation between employee job satisfaction and adhocracy culture.

In addition to the above-mentioned findings, the participants of the study discussed the low bureaucratic barriers and high level of autonomy, as Respondent (12) quoted "I am more of self-directed in my job position". In support of this claim Respondent (15) noted that "In my position I am able to work faster, as there are limited (less) processes that I go through. And, less bureaucracy for me to go through". This claim is explained by the literature within the field of organizational studies, where [21] asserted lack bureaucracy allows employees to carry out their daily tasks easily, as there is no authority or centralized power within the adhocracy culture of Emerald. On the contrary, the continuous change of environment is resulting in decreased employee job satisfaction and performance, as underlined by Respondent (15); "Whenever you start your job these is a massive list of to-do tasks, but when you are about to start, all of a sudden you get a call from a senior manager asking you to drop everything and finish what they have asked you to do". In retrospect, the research propounded that hierarchy culture still exists in the office-based environment of Emerald, and managers continue to decide the allocation of tasks and how it should be done and when it should be done by. This gives rise to the claim that there is a positive relationship between the hierarchy and adhocracy culture, which was also highlighted in the study of [47].

B. Impact of Clan Culture on Employee Job Satisfaction

The findings of the qualitative research discovered that employees were motivated through team working, cohesion, loyalty and trust, as Respondent (6) stressed "I love my job mainly because of the team working and trust that I have with my co-workers". This illustrates that clan culture plays a key

role in facilitating employee job satisfaction in Emerald through a boosting relationship. This is also backed by the literature, for example, the work of [52] found that employees who were happy and satisfied in their workplaces performed well in their roles. In addition to that, these findings support the claim that having a good organization culture can be vital for employee job satisfaction, as it creates the right environment [47]. Furthermore, these findings proposed the idea that the relationship between clan culture and employee job satisfaction is stronger than that of adhocracy culture, which contrasts with [1]'s research.

The office-based environment of Emerald was perceived to be controlled by clan culture where employees enjoyed their jobs and felt satisfaction, which lead to better performance, as employees felt motivated. This is well exemplified by Respondent (3) who claimed that "My managers are very helpful and they guide me constantly to develop my career, which makes me want to go that extra mile and work to the best of my ability". This argument is backed by the literature, where [7] stated that organizational culture that appreciates and values its employees will improve their performance. The literature and findings have demonstrated that valuing the workforce can be vital in the longer term, as Respondent (6) underlined "It is true, if people work in a team happily it motivates me too and want to be part of it and do well". In conclusion, these claims provide empirical evidence to back the notion that satisfied and happy employees are more productive, and acknowledges that motivated employees are more satisfied and productive [12]. Furthermore, this authenticates the argument of [2] that motivation is vital to increasing employee job satisfaction and productivity as a whole.

C. Impact of Hierarchy Culture on Employee Job Satisfaction

The findings of this subjectivist study suggested that hierarchy culture has a bad/weak influence on employee job satisfaction in Emerald, as the interviewees felt restricted due to the bureaucratic environment. This is well validated by Respondent (14) who asserted "That I have worked here over a long period of time and for the first five years I have experienced restriction, because every time I did something, I was told that is not how we do it and it is not allowed in here". It is indicated that the effects of hierarchy culture on employee job satisfaction is not good and is creating a sense of inability to be able to carry out their jobs and to experience a sense of incompetence, which ultimately results in employee dissatisfaction [32]. Adding to these, the interviewees at the bottom of the hierarchy felt they were not well informed about the decisions that affected their work-life. This is backed by Respondent (10) who stated, "The information comes from senior managers and by the time it reaches the middle managers a lot of the information is lost or just not passed on, which creates a sense of unawareness and unhappiness". It is shown that throughout the hierarchy, the flow of information is poor, which leads to employee job dissatisfaction.

Even though the overall influence of hierarchy culture on

employee job satisfaction was undesirable, there were certain elements that resulted in satisfaction; namely, a sense of security and structure, as Respondent (13) added, "I feel like we are safe and secure in our jobs because everything is structured and the environment is quite stable too". This also contributes to the literature, as [52] noted employee feel satisfied if they are safe. Nonetheless, the finding contradicts [10]'s findings, as he found that hierarchy culture had the lowest level of employee job satisfaction. The findings of this qualitative study also contrast of [47] and [48]'s research, where they discovered hierarchy culture to be causing dissatisfaction. In their study of organizational culture and employee productivity, [1] mentioned that although the hierarchy culture provides employees with the structure and methods to be productive, the bottom line employees tend to suffer in such culture, as their interests are not considered. In retrospect, the researcher found that the hierarchy culture is not good fit for Emerald's culture, as it creates employee job dissatisfaction and restricts their ability to perform better.

D. Impact of Market Culture on Employee Job Satisfaction

The interviewees who participated in this study demonstrated an adverse relationship between the market culture and the office-based environment of Emerald through the high demands of job and constant pressure. This was well-exemplified by Respondent (9) who argued, "I feel like Emerald has too much expectations from us employees". Similarly, Respondent (15) claimed that "I think the culture of Emerald is individualistic and there is too much pressure, which has been banded around me and if I do not work towards it then I will be gone". This makes employees feel dissatisfied, supporting [47] and [48]'s studies which found corresponding effects. However, the market culture comes with internal and external pressure which creates a good impact on employee performance in an office-based environment, as this was highlighted by Respondent (13) who affirmed, "Because there is so much pressure on me I have to work extra hard to meet those expectations and it can only be achieved if I am more productive". It is indicated that the pressure put on employees makes them work harder and encourages them at times. This is particularly demonstrated by Respondent (8) who illuminated, "In a culture where everyone around me works hard, it will make me want to work more hard and put that extra pressure on me to do more work". This claim is not backed by the literature, as [12] inferred that employees put under pressure will result in job dissatisfaction and lead to stress, which will ultimately impact on performance. The researcher concluded that employees in Emerald did not like the elements of market culture as it was leading to job dissatisfaction through constant pressure and high expectations.

VII. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The main driving force of this qualitative study was to explore the role of organizational culture in facilitating employee job satisfaction at Emerald Publishing Group. This exploratory study brought in professional and personal

interests along with a business need within an organizational culture in a worldwide recognized publication group (Emerald). Its findings added to the existing, albeit limited, body of knowledge on organizational culture and its impact on employee job satisfaction in an office-based environment.

The findings of the qualitative data indicated that the majority of interviewees perceive the culture within Emerald to be dominated by not only adhocracy culture but also clan culture characteristics such as HR development, team working, cohesion, loyalty and trust. In terms of the level of job satisfaction the researcher propounded that a clear level of employee job satisfaction was not present in Emerald, as the majority of the interviewees claimed that the level of employee job satisfaction relied on various factors, such as rewards (benefits, recognition and appreciation), pay, motivation and clear communication. In conclusion, the findings provided evidence, which demonstrated that organizational culture plays a key role in facilitating employee job satisfaction in a service-based environment.

Despite the contributions of this study, a few limitations and areas for future research were highlighted. Firstly, the findings of this study are hard to be generalizable due to the qualitative approach of the study. It is suggested that future studies should be replicated on a large sample using preponderant same size and quantitative questionnaires to enhance the validity and generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, the researcher of this study identified codes that emerged from the interviews. Most of these codes included, bonuses and pay rise, delegation, burnout or stress, work-life balance, prioritization of work and rationalization, office space and the availability of resources. It is suggested and encouraged that these codes are taken into consideration for future studies, as the interviewees, emphasizing significance, raised them independently.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. K. R. S. Shooshtri, Exploring the Effect of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction: Case of Namvaran Consulting Engineers, Managers Company. *Master's Thesis*: Luleå University of Technology, 2016.
- [2] M. Armstrong and S. Taylor, *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. (14th edition), London: Kogan Page Publishers, 2017.
- [3] S. A. Zahra, J. C. Hayton, J. C., & C. Salvato, Entrepreneurship in family vs. Non-Family firms: A Resource-Based analysis of the effect of organizational culture. *Journal of Entrepreneurship theory and Practice*, 28 (4), 363-381, 2004.
- [4] T. Redman, and A. Wilkinson, *Contemporary Human Resource Management* – Text and Cases. (5th edition) London: Pearson, 2017.
- [5] Emerald, *Emerald Group Publishing*. (online) Available at: <http://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/> (Accessed 28 May 2018), 2018.
- [6] G. Hofstede, *Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviours, institutions, and organizations across nations*. (2nd edition). Thousands Oaks, CA: SAGE, 2001.
- [7] T. J. Peters, & R.H Waterman, *In search of excellence*. New York: Harper & Row, 1982.
- [8] W. Ouchi, *Theory z: How American business can meet the Japanese challenge?* Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1981.
- [9] T.E. Deal, and A.A. Kennedy, *Corporate Cultures. The Rites and Rituals of Organizational Life*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1982.
- [10] D. B. Lund, Organizational culture and job satisfaction. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 18 (3), 219-236, 2003.
- [11] S. A. Booth, and K. Hamer, Corporate culture and financial performance: an empirical test of a UK retailer. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 37(8), pp.711-727, 2009.
- [12] E. Ogbonna, E. and L. C., Subcultural tensions in managing organizational culture: a study of an English Premier League football organization. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 25 (2): 217–232, 2015.
- [13] M. H. Tayeb, *The Management of a Multicultural Workforce*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 1996.
- [14] C. Xiaoming, and X. Junchen, A Literature Review on Organizational Culture and Corporate Performance. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 3(2), 29-37, 2012.
- [15] D. Ravasi, M. Schultz, Responding to Organizational Identity Threats: Exploring the Role of Organizational Culture. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(3), 433-458, 2006.
- [16] R. Deshpande, and Jr, F.E., Webster, Organizational culture and marketing: defining the research agenda. *Journal of marketing*, 53(1), pp.3-15, 1989.
- [17] E. H. Schein, *Organizational culture and leadership*. (3rd edition). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2004.
- [18] X. Zhang, and B. Li, Organizational Culture and Employee job satisfaction: An Exploratory Study. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 4 (1): 48-54, 2013.
- [19] A. Aldhuwailhi, The influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention: a study on the banking sector in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *PhD thesis*: Victoria University, 2013.
- [20] G. Hofstede, Motivation, leadership, and organization: Do American theories apply abroad?. *Organizational Dynamics*, 9(1), 42-63, 1981.
- [21] K. Cameron, and R Quinn, R. *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework*. (3rd edition). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass, 2011.
- [22] R. Quinn, and J. Rohrbaugh, A spatial model of effectiveness criteria: Towards a competing values approach to organizational analysis. *Management Science*, 29(3), 363- 77, 1983.
- [23] S. Robbins, T. A. Judge, B. Millett, and M. Boyle, Organizational behaviour. Pearson role of organizational culture. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49, 433-458, 2013.
- [24] K. Cameron, and S. Freeman, Cultural congruence, strength and type: Relationships of effectiveness. In W. Pasmore, & R. Woodman, (Eds.), *Research in organizational change and development* (pp. 23-58). Greenwich, CT: JAI Press, 1991.
- [25] E. Schein, *Organizational culture and leadership*. (2nd edition). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass Publishers, 1992.
- [26] E. W. MacIntosh, and A. Doherty, The influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction and intention to leave. *Sport Management Review*, 13(2), pp.106-117, 2010.
- [27] U. Colakoglu, O. Culha, and H. Atay, The effects of perceived organizational support on employees affective outcomes: evidence from the hotel industry. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Management* 16, 125–150, 2010.
- [28] R. Toga, The Relationship between Job Involvement, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Among Lower-Level Employees at Mercedes Benz South Africa. *Doctoral dissertation*, University of Fort Hare, 2011.
- [29] J.D. Thompson, *Organizations in action: Social science bases of administrative theory*. Routledge, 2017.
- [30] F.H. Yang, and C.C. Chang, Emotional labour, job satisfaction and organizational commitment amongst clinical nurses: a questionnaire survey. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 45, 879–887, 2008.
- [31] R. Vecchio, *Organizational behaviour*. New York, NY: Dryden Press, 1995.
- [32] E. Locke, The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In M. Dunnette, (Ed.). *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology*. Chicago, IL: Rand McNally, 1976.
- [33] P. Smith, L. Kendall, and C. Hulin, *Measurement of satisfaction in work and retirement*. Chicago, IL: Rand McNally, 1969.
- [34] L. Aiken, D. Havens, D. Sloane, The magnet nursing services recognition program: A comparison of two groups of magnet hospitals. *American Journal of Nursing*, 100 (3), pp. 26-36, 2000.
- [35] B. Verplanken, Value congruence and job satisfaction among nurses: A human relations perspective. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 41, pp. 74-92, 2004.
- [36] R. Y. Odom, W. R. Box, M. G. Dunn, Organizational cultures, commitment, satisfaction and cohesion. *Public Productivity Management Review*, 14, pp. 157-69, 1990.
- [37] C. Silverthorne, The impact of organizational culture and

- personorganization fit on organizational commitment and job satisfaction in Taiwan. Leadership amp; *Organization Development Journal*, 25, pp. 592-9, 2004.
- [38] I. C. Huang, J. M. Wu, The corporate culture and its effects on organizational commitment and job satisfaction in public sector: An example of the Taiwan Tobacco and Liquor Monopoly Bureau. *Review of Public- Owned Enterprises*, 2 (1), pp. 25-46, 2000.
- [39] E. A. Platonova, R.S Hernandez, R. M. Shewchuk, K. M. Leddy, Study of relationship between organizational culture and organizational outcomes using hierarchical linear modeling methodology. *Quality Management in Health Care*, 15 (3), pp. 200-9, 2006.
- [40] L. J. McKinnon, L. G. Harrison, W. C. Chow, A. Wu, Organizational culture: Association with commitment, job satisfaction propensity to remain and information sharing in Taiwan. *International Journal of Business Studies*, 11 (1), pp. 25-44, 2003.
- [41] V. Bellou, Achieving long- term customer satisfaction through organizational culture: Evidence from health care sector. *Managing Service Quality*, 17 (5), pp. 510-22, 2007.
- [42] M.O. Olasupo, Relationship between Organizational Culture, Leadership Style and Job Satisfaction in a Nigerian Manufacturing Organization. *IFE Centre for Psychological Studies*, 19 (1), 159-176, 2011.
- [43] S. Habib, S. Aslam, A. Hussain, S. Yasmeen, and M. Ibrahim, The Impact of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction, Employees Commitment and Turn over Intention. *Journal of Advances in Economics and Business*, 2(6): 215-222, 2014.
- [44] F. Daniel, and A. Purwanti, The impact of organizational culture and job satisfaction to organizational commitment and employee's job performance. *An Empirical Study at A University: Tangerang*, 2015.
- [45] I. Palmer, R. Dunford, and D. Buchanan, *Managing Organizational Change: A Multiple Perspective Approach* (3rd edition). Boston: McGraw Hill, 2016.
- [46] K.R. Sowmya and N. Panchanatham, Factors influencing job satisfaction of banking sector employees in Chennai, India. *Journal of Law and Conflict Resolution*, 3(5), 76-79, 2011.
- [47] M. Fatima, The Impact of Organizational Culture Types on the Job Satisfaction of Employees. *Sukkur IBA Journal of Management and Business*, 3 (1), 13-32, 2016.
- [48] A. Azam, Impact of Organizational Culture Type on Job Satisfaction Level of Employees' in Different Organizations of Lahore, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 2 (12), 97-112, 2012.
- [49] E.A Amos, and B.L. Weathington, An analysis of the relation between employee organization value congruence and Employee Attitudes. *The journal of psychology*, 142(6), 615-631, 2008.
- [50] J. W. Creswell, *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: choosing among five approaches*. (3rd edition). London: SAGE, 2013.
- [51] J. Collis, and R. Hussey, *Business Research: a practical guide for undergraduate & postgraduate students*. (4th edition). Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan, 2014.
- [52] A. Maslow, A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370- 96, 1954.
- [53] P.E., Spector, Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences (Vol. 3). Sage publications.